

PICK A PERSON USER INSIGHT AND DESIGN FOR WELLBEING THROUGH PERSONALITY PSYCHOLOGY

John Magnus Roos
Veryday
Centre for Consumer Science, University of Gothenburg
✉ Magnus.Roos@Veryday.com

Diana Africano Clark
Veryday
✉ Diana.Africano.Clark@Veryday.com

ABSTRACT

In this paper we describe a non-verbal personality instrument for user-centred design that consists of 10 extreme cartoon-like characters. The theoretical framework for the characters is The Big Five personality model: openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism. Each of the five dimensions has two extremities; open-minded versus closed-minded; conscientious versus impulsive; extrovert versus introvert; agreeable versus antagonistic; neurotic versus emotionally stable. During explorative interviews the user is free to pick the personality character(s) that correspond to who he or she is at present when interacting with a certain product, service, system or environment. Additionally the user picks the characters that correspond to who he/she would ideally like to be when interacting with the same research object. The aim of the method is to provide insight into what design aspects may bridge the gap that resides in the mismatch between the individual's real and ideal self, thereby facilitating wellbeing-driven design.

KEYWORDS: *pictorial, non-verbal, personality, self, user-centered design*

INTRODUCTION

Psychologists have a long tradition of developing personality tests that measure who people are. These tests have mostly been used by recruiting agencies and Public Health Institutions in order to predict health problems and addictive behaviour. Nowadays, verbal personality tests are increasingly used in quantitative business and design studies in order to receive insights about user behaviour (i.e. Sing & Das, 2009; Xu & Montague, 2012; Roos, 2013). Verbal personality tests usually consist of a large number of statements, sometimes several pages, in which the user responds to what level he or she agrees or disagrees. So far, personality tests have not been associated with qualitative user-studies, simply because they have not been designed for such purposes. The present study argues that reshaping and adjusting these personality tests to be more user-study might create new opportunities for user input in people-driven design, especially when the focus is on subjective wellbeing and personal growth.

PERSONALITY THEORIES

The real self and the ideal self

The central concepts in Carl Roger's theory of personality are the real self and the ideal self. The real self consists of all the ideas, perceptions and values that characterize "I" or "me"; it includes the awareness of "what I am". The ideal self is our conception of the kind of person we would like to be. Our perceived real and ideal selves very seldom match. The inevitable gap that this mismatch generates causes various degrees of unpleasant affect and health problems. A greater understanding of what is at each end of this personal polarity, and extensively what bridges it, gives us new tools to design for subjective wellbeing. According to Roger (1951), the closer the real self is to the ideal self, the more fulfilled and happy the individual becomes. A large discrepancy between the real self and the ideal self results in an unhappy and dissatisfied person (Atkinson et al, 2000).

The Big Five

The Big Five is the taxonomy of personality traits that has received the most attention and support from personality researchers and personality theorists. According to the Big Five model, all human characters can be categorized into five broad personality dimensions; Openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism (Larsen and Buss, 2005). According to Larsen and Buss (2005), key markers of the Big Five are as follows:

1. **Openness (versus reticence).** Open individuals are open for innovations, different cultures and the emotions of other people, while closed individuals are more conservative and closed in terms of the emotions of other people.
2. **Conscientiousness (versus impulsivity).** Conscientious individuals are industrious and think ahead. They are organized, neat and prompt, while spontaneous people are more careless and disorderly.
3. **Extraversion (versus introversion).** Extroverts love to party, they engage in frequent social interaction, take the lead in livening up dull gatherings, and enjoy talking a lot. Introverts are more shy and quiet, and tend to be more like wallflowers.
4. **Agreeableness (versus disagreeableness).** Agreeable individuals get along well with others, are well liked, avoid conflicts, strive for harmony, while disagreeable people are aggressive, unsympathetic and seem to get themselves into a lot of social conflicts.
5. **Neuroticism (versus emotional stability).** Emotionally stable individuals are calm, relaxed and stable, while emotionally unstable individuals are moody, anxious and insecure.

A NON-VERBAL PERSONALITY TOOL

Development of the tool

Our ambition has been to create unisexual and multicultural characters, free from physical objects and symbols (e.g. clothes and hairstyles). We have combined personality theories with knowledge regarding body language and facial expressions (i.e. Axtell, 1998; Ekman and Friesen, 2003; Navarro and Karllins, 2008; Pease and Pease, 2004), and used Internet and comic magazines as inspiration.

Different versions of the characters have been tested in six different pilot studies ($n \approx 20$ student per study) at the University of Gothenburg and Stockholm University, and continuously improved by graphic designers at Veryday, a design agency in Sweden. Altogether we have developed ten personality characters and one neutral (Figure 1). The first five characters (e.g. closed-minded, impulsive, extrovert, antagonistic and neurotic) have been validated against 143 undergraduate Swedish students at the University of Gothenburg. Their counterparts (e.g. open-minded, conscientious, introvert, agreeable, emotionally stable) have only been validated against 32 under-

Figure 1. Ten non-verbal personality characters and neutral.

graduate Swedish students at the University of Gothenburg. We view the validation of the counterparts as a pilot study.

Validation of the tool

The validation process included content validity, criterion validity and construct validity (Laurans, 2011). The content validation of the non-verbal scale is based on tag clouds of adjectives from top-of-mind responses (i.e. responses to the question “*which three adjectives do you best think describe this person?*”). The tag clouds have been compared to the general framework of the Big Five model of personalities. The criterion validation of the non-verbal scale is based on the equivalence between this scale and an established verbal scale of the Big Five model of personalities, the HP5i (Gustavsson, Jönsson, Linder and Weinryb, 2008; Holmberg and Weibull, 2010). In the validation process, the perceived personality of each character was measured by all HP5-15 items (Table 1). The scale used for each item was a four-level scale; completely agree (coded as 1), partly agree (coded as 2), partly disagree (coded as 3), completely disagree (coded as 4). For the criterion validity to be satisfactory, the three items measuring the particular factor must have an average of 1,5 (i.e. between completely agree and partly agree). Construct validity refers to how the extremities are constructed and how they differ from each other. Ideally, the items used to measure one extremity should be as different as possible but have high correlation among themselves (convergent validity) while the correlations between different extremities (and items) should be as low as possible (divergent validity). Also the construct validation of the non-verbal scale is based on convergent validity and divergent validity in relation to HP5i. For the convergent validity to be satisfactory, the correlation

PERSONALITY TRAIT	ITEMS IN HP5
Openness (reverse scale)	I think emotions are often exaggerated
	I often have difficulties in understanding other's feelings
	Normally, I avoid getting involved in others' problems
Conscientiousness (reverse scale)	I usually act on the spur of the moment
	I often throw myself too hastily into things
	I usually talk before I think
Extraversion	I often feel exhilarated
	I usually enjoy life
	I am usually in a good mood when I socialize
Agreeableness (reverse scale)	I often make sarcastic remarks
	I usually behave vengefully if I am treated badly
	I usually come up with piercing and malicious answers
Neuroticism	I often feel uncomfortable and ill at ease
	I often feel pressure when I have to speed up
	My muscles are often so tense that I get tired

Table 1. Link between personality dimensions and items
Source: Gustavsson, Jönsson, Linder and Weinryb, 2008; Holmberg and Weibull, 2010

of the three items measuring a particular dimension (Table 1) should be as high as possible. But they also have to capture the broadness of that specific dimension (for instance openness), rather than measuring the same thing. For the divergent validity to be satisfactory, the mean of the three items (Table 1) should correspond more to the dimension it is supposed to measure than to other dimensions. In other words, the dimensions should be mutually exclusive.

The validation process of the first five characters has been presented at five international conferences (Roos, 2012a; 2012b; 2013; 2014; Roos, Nilsson & Whetley, 2013). To summarize our findings, the neurotic character scores high on all three validity measures. The extrovert character and the antagonistic character scored low on content validity. The impulsive character scored low on construct validity. The most problematic character was the closed-minded, which scored low on both validity and construct validity.

GENERAL DISCUSSION

Currently we validate all 10 characters (Figure 1). We have made some modifications of the first five since the last validation (Roos, 2013), in order to receive higher criterion validity. We have also added a neutral character, to be used in the introduction of the test in order to avoid the perception of the first character to be influenced by general characteristics, such as hairless and undressed. We also worked with the graphic design aesthetics in order to synchronize the eleven characters. The shape of faces and hands differ somewhat (Figure 1), which might have threatened our effort to develop unisexual and multicultural characters.

The reason for our ambitious validation effort was, and is, that we would like to cover the variety in human beings. The Big Five model has successfully been able to capture the variety in humanity, across time and cultures (Larsen & Buss, 2005). If we are able to develop a non-verbal personality tool that corresponds to the Big Five personality model, we are able to give the respondents a simple, but still comprehensive, tool to express themselves.

Despite an ambitious validation effort, we are not searching for an ultimate truth shared by all individuals. When using the instrument, the primary focus is not to find out whom a person is through his or her life, based on some kind of scientific objectivity. We do not think that such truths exist in either verbal or non-verbal languages (e.g. facial expressions and body language). The advantages of using the characters are that they open up discussions in an interview context and help researchers interact and uncover aspects of use, tacit knowledge, and latent needs that users are otherwise unwilling and/or unable to verbally express. This is especially true when it comes to associations, personal desires, needs and feelings, and when it comes to anticipations of the future as opposed to reflections of the past. So far, the characters have been used as “personality cards”, especially in explorative research settings (Roos, Nilsson & Whetley, 2013). The users are free to interpret the characters, and we primarily focus on why the users pick and combine specific cards,

We believe that designers, as well as psychologists, can contribute to subjective wellbeing, but first they have to know what makes people happy. We use the personality cards to explore potential discrepancies between the user's real self and ideal self (Roos, Nilsson & Whetley, 2013). Such input

helps us design for the user's wellbeing in accordance with Carl Roger's self-theory (1951). Our experience is that the personality cards make it easier for users to express who they are, both in general and in relation to the study object. Our experience is that the cards also make it easier for users to talk about their ideal self, or who they want to be, both in the world they perceive and in the world they dream about. The users' dreams and aspirations open up for business opportunities, both related to individual- and environmental change. Therefore, the input can stimulate all kind of design solutions (i.e. product-, service-, interactive-, digital solutions).

Unlike existing personality tests, this test is adjusted for interviews and co-creation sessions, and combines the real and ideal selves, rather than only focusing on the real self. Unlike current non-verbal tools used in the design field (e.g. SAM emotional response measurement manikin, PrEmo measure product emotions), this tool focuses more on aspirations within individuals rather than appraisals of stimuli.

CONCLUSION

Our conclusion is that the pictorial characters help users to express their personality, which might not always be easy to do with the use of words alone. However, the validation process of the ten characters is not yet completed and more effort is needed in order to investigate to what degree the presented pictorial assessment actually corresponds to the theoretical framework of the Big Five.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are greatly indebted to Riksbankens Jubileumsfond in Stockholm for providing funding. The authors would also like to thank colleges at Veryday for fruitful discussions and support, especially Henrik Olsson, graphic designer at Veryday.

REFERENCES

Atkinson, R. L., Atkinson, R. C., Smith, D. J., Bem, D. J., Nolen-Hoeksema, S. (2000). *Hilgard's Introduction to Psychology*. New York, NY: Harcourt College Publishers.

Axtell, R. E. (1998). *Gestures. The Do's and Taboos of Body Language Around the World*. New York: John Wiley & Sons.

Ekman, P., Friesen, M. V. (2003). *Unmasking the Face. A Guide to Recognizing Emotions from Facial Expressions*. Cambridge, MA: Malor Books.

Navarro, J., Karlins, M. (2008). *What Every Body is Saying*, New York, NY: Harper.

Gustavsson, J. P., Jönsson, E. G., Linder, J., Weinryb, R. M. (2003). The HP5 inventory: definition and assessment of five health-relevant personality traits from a five-factor model perspective. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 35, 69-89.

Holmberg, S., Weibull, L. (2010). Människans fem personlighetsegenskaper. In S. Holmberg and L. Weibull. (Eds.) *Nordiskt ljus*, p. 323-328. Gothenburg, SE: SOM Institute, University of Gothenburg.

Larsen, R. J., Buss, D. M. (2005). *Personality Psychology: Domain of Knowledge about Human Nature*. New York, NY: McGraw-Hill.

Laurans, G. (2011). *On the moment-to-moment measurement of emotion during person-product interaction*. Doctoral dissertation, Delft Technische Universiteit Delft, the Netherlands.

Pease, A., Pease, B. (2004). *The definitive book of body language*, New York, NY: Bantam Books.

Roger, C. R. (1951). *Client-centered therapy*. Boston, MA: Houghton Mifflin.

Roos, J. M. (2012a). A visual personification of personalities. *AAPOR67: Abstract proceedings of 67th Annual Conference of America Association for Public Opinion Research*, 17-20 May, Orlando, United States of America.

Roos, J. M. (2012b). The "Big Five" personified. *ICP30: Abstract proceeding of 30th International Congress of Psychology*, 22-27 July, Cape Town, South Africa.

Roos, J. M. (2013). Verification of Very 5: A non-verbal personality scale. *ECP13: Abstract proceeding of 13th European Congress of Psychology*, 9-12 July, Stockholm, Sweden.

Roos, J. M. (2014). Validation of ten non-verbal personality extremities. *Abstract proceeding of Australian Statistical Conference in conjunction with the Institute of Mathematical Statistics Annual Meeting*, 7-10 July, Sydney, Australia

Roos, J. M. (2013). Bilmärke, genus och personlighet. In: L. Weibull, H. Oscarsson, A. Bergström (Eds.). *Vägskäl*. Gothenburg, Sweden: Ale tryckteam, 401-411.

Roos, J. M., Nilsson, T., Wheatley, E. (2013). Express your selves. Personality cards as a research tool to explore the user's real and ideal self. *IASDR5: Proceedings in the 5th International Congress of International Association of Society of Design Research*, 26-30 August, Tokyo, Japan.

Sing, A., Das, L. K. (2009). A framework of biker-bike personality factors within social culture of biking in India. *IASDR 2009: Proceedings of International Association of Society of Design Research*, 18-22 October, Seoul, Korea.

Xu, J., Montague, E. (2012). Psychophysiology of the passive user: Exploring the effect of technological conditions and personality traits. *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics*, 42, 505-512.